

UTILIZING LEARNING GUIDE IN TEACHING ECONOMICS AND THE REFLECTIVE THINKING SKILLS OF THE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The main goal of this study was to determine a significant relationship between the assessments of the students in the existing learning guide as to its components and their perceptions in the manifested reflective thinking skills in Araling Panlipunan 9/Ekonomiks? This study made use of the descriptive-correlational design. The respondents consisted of 100 Grade 9 students who is studying in Sta. Anastacia – San Rafael National High School in the District of Batangas. The questionnaire was completed using Google Forms by the respondents. Mean, standard deviation and Pearson Product Moment Correlation were used to analyze the responses of the students. The respondent assessed the existing learning guide in Araling Panlipunan 9/Ekonomiks revealed that there is significant relationship between the student's perception in the use of Learning Guide on components and reflective thinking skills through content, design and format (M= 4.32) and (r=.597), through instructional design (M=4.32) and (r=.600), through methodology (M=4.35) and (r=.551), through social considerations (M=4.47) (r=.556) all interpreted "acceptable." As to the perceived level of students with the reflective thinking skills in terms of Relating new knowledge to prior understanding (M=4.32) and (r=.555), Thinking in both abstract and conceptual terms (M=4.37) and (r=.571), Applying specific strategies in novel tasks (M=4.37) and (r=.579), and understanding own thinking and learning strategies (M=4.38) and (r=.587), all interpreted as "to a great extent". Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2- tailed). The hypothesis stating that there is no significant relationship between the assessments of the students in the existing learning guide as to its components and their perceptions in the manifested reflective thinking skills in Araling Panlipunan 9/Ekonomiks is not accepted as supported by evidences. It is recommended that the result of this study shall be utilized by not only the educational institutions but also by the teachers, use the result of this study to better guide and teach their students as they use the existing learning guides and learning skills.

Keywords: learning guides, araling panlipunan, reflective thinking